

EFFICIENCY OF CAGE AND FLOOR TECHNOLOGY FOR BROILER CHICKEN GROWING

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Annotation: The organization of industrial production of poultry products involves the creation of conditions provided by technology for the cultivation and maintenance of poultry, complex mechanization of labor-intensive processes, maintaining continuity, rhythmicity of the production process, maximum use of the biological capabilities of poultry, achieving a high live weight of broiler chickens at the lowest cost of labor and feed. The article deals with the study of the influence of various methods of keeping broiler chickens on the formation of microclimate in poultry houses, their growth rate, safety, feed costs per 1 kg of growth, the European index of cultivation efficiency. The live weight of broiler chickens at the end of cultivation (40 days) in the experimental group was 2650 g, which is 13.3 % higher than the control

group. The average daily increase was higher in broiler chickens in the experimental poultry house by 13.4 %, compared with the control. The feed conversion per 1 kg of increase was 1.68 kg in the control poultry house, and 1.61 kg in the experimental one, which is 4.4 % less. The slaughter yield is 1.2 % higher in the experimental poultry house. The production of carcasses of the first category is greater in the experimental poultry house than in the control one and amounts to 70.8 % and 65.7 %, respectively. It was found that the European efficiency index for two poultry houses was high, while in the experimental poultry house it was 366 weeks, and in the control 348, which is lower by 18 weeks. The safety of broiler chickens for 40 days of cultivation was 95.7 in the control poultry house, 92.8 % in the experimental one, which is 3.1 % lower.

Key words: broiler chickens, microclimate, live weight, average daily growth, feed costs, safety, European productivity index.

When comparing the effectiveness of cellular and floor technologies, the cost of buildings, external and internal engineering communications, etc. is often not taken into account. Calculations show that the costs for these purposes are three times higher with floor maintenance and, in total with the cost of equipment, significantly exceed the cost of cell technology per 1 thousand seats. It is necessary to proceed from the fact that the main task in organizing the technological process of growing broilers is to obtain the maximum yield of marketable products per unit area of the poultry house with minimal labor and cost. Obviously, the wrong decision and financial miscalculation in the face of growing competition can lead to large economic losses. So, it can be stated that the broiler cage technology is a significant reserve for a rapid and significant increase in meat production. The advantage of this technology, in comparison with the floor technology, is the maximum use of production areas, a high level of mechanization and automation of production processes, reducing the cost of engineering communications, heating and lighting of the premises, improving sanitary and veterinary conditions, increasing the yield of meat per unit area by 2, 5-3 times.

When rearing in cages, no litter is required, better observation of the bird is ensured, chicks do not come into contact with waste and are less likely to become

infected with parasites, especially coccidia. In cages, broiler chickens grow better, consume less feed per unit of growth, more early terms reach lethal conditions. In addition, the work of workers is facilitated, labor costs for servicing and sending poultry for slaughter are reduced. Abroad, meat chickens are usually grown on deep litter, where cage technology is not widely used. But today, highly productive auto-sex domestic crosses of meat chickens have been created, adapted not only to floor, but also to cell growing technology. Therefore, we can state: there are all conditions for the widespread introduction of cell technology for the production of chicken meat.

In addition, serial production of modern multi-tiered cage batteries with automatic unloading of poultry for slaughter has been mastered, where manual catching and removal of birds from cages are excluded, the period for growing broilers has been reduced to 35-40 days, optimal technological parameters have been determined for joint and separate keeping of poultry in cages. A technology for deep processing of meat has been introduced, which makes it possible to use non-standard carcasses for this purpose and, most importantly, helps to increase the profitability of production up to 20-25%. In the EU countries, at the request of numerous public organizations for the protection of animals and the environment, broilers are grown mainly using outdoor technologies, which are considered somewhat more humane than cell technologies. So, as with cell growing technologies, chest or leg injuries appear on the carcasses of some broilers. There are also broilers with damage to the wings and legs, which they receive during removal from the cages when shipped for slaughter. The cage technology of growing broilers has a number of advantages over the floor technology of growing. These advantages consist in a more rational use of the production area of poultry houses (2.5-3.0 times increase in product yield per unit area), a high level of mechanization and automation of production processes, reducing the cost of engineering communications, ensuring standard microclimate parameters (temperature, lighting, air exchange, etc.) and the best sanitary and veterinary conditions. Cage technology does not require litter and provides a better level of control over the general condition of the bird. They do not come into contact with litter and therefore are less likely to get coccidiosis. With cage technologies, chickens become less mobile and therefore

spend less feed energy on movements, using it to increase body weight, and therefore reach slaughter conditions faster.

The most important problem in the agro-industrial complex of the country is to increase the production of meat, including poultry. It can be solved not only by optimizing the genetic and paratypic factors that affect the bird's body. One of the determining factors in increasing productivity is proper feeding and, in particular, the use of biologically active agents.

Recently, in agriculture, the problem of the need to introduce resource-saving technologies for keeping and feeding poultry has increasingly arisen. One of the directions in their solution is the use of chlorella biomass as a vitamin-feed additive and a prophylactic agent against diseases. The introduction of it in the form of a suspension in the diet of poultry can largely replace expensive vitamin and medicinal preparations.

On the basis of the conducted studies, it was found that the cage content of broiler chickens has an advantage over the outdoor one in terms of live weight gain at the end of fattening and slaughter yield. The capacity of the premises is also increased with less labor costs. The live weight of broiler chickens at the end of rearing (40 days) in the experimental group was 2650 g, which is 13.3% higher than in the control group. The average daily gain was higher for broiler chickens in the experimental poultry house by 13.4% compared to the control one.

Feed conversion per 1 kg of growth was 1.68 kg in the control poultry house, and 1.61 kg in the experimental one, which is 4.4% less. The slaughter yield is higher in the experimental poultry house by 1.2%. Receiving carcasses of the first category is more in the experimental poultry house than in the control one and is 70.8% and 65.7%, respectively. It was established that the European efficiency index for two poultry houses was high, while in the experimental poultry house it was 366 units, and in the control one it was 348, which is 18 units lower. The safety of broiler chickens for 40 days of growing was 95.7% in the control poultry house, 92.8% in the experimental one, which is 3.1% lower. During the hygienic assessment of the conditions for keeping

broiler chickens, we studied the state and dynamics of the formation of the microclimate in the poultry house, live weight in samples from both groups (50 heads were estimated in each group), absolute and average daily gain, feed costs for gaining 1 kg of live weight.

Monitoring of the main indicators of the microclimate in poultry houses indicates that they comply with hygienic requirements. To assess the growth rates of broiler chickens, we analyzed the data on live weight. indicate that the live weight of the chickens of the experimental group at the age of two weeks exceeded the control group by 5.4% and amounted to 531.6 g. 3 g. At the end of the experiment (40 days), the live weight of broiler chickens in the experimental group was 2650 g, which is 13.3% higher than in the control group. One of the main parameters characterizing the intensity of poultry growth is the average daily gain in live weight, which is represented by.

Analyzing the data , it can be seen that the feed conversion per 1 kg of gain was 1.68 kg in the control poultry house, and 1.61 kg in the experimental one, which is 4.4% less. The slaughter yield is higher in the experimental poultry house by 1.2%. Receiving carcasses of the first category is more in the experimental poultry house than in the control one and is 70.8% and 65.7%, respectively. It was found that the European efficiency index for two poultry houses was high and increased from 348 to 366 units with different growing methods.

Thus, on the basis of the studies, it was found that the cage content of broiler chickens, in comparison with the floor content, contributes to an increase in live weight gain at the end of fattening and slaughter yield, density of chickens and higher feed conversion, however, lower safety is observed.

List of used literature:

1. Frolov, A. N. Production of broiler meat: pract. leadership / A. N. Frolov. - M.: Agrosprom, 2010. - 128 p.

2. Ilyina, Z. Prospects for the development of the poultry meat market in the context of global trends / Z. Ilyina, L. Yonchik // Agrar. economy. - 2010. - No. 9. - S. 24-60.

3. . Teslova, V. On some aspects of poultry enterprises of the Republic of Belarus / V. Teslova // Agrar. economy. - 2012. - N ° 2. - S. 14-17.

